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Rethinking openness: a social constructivist approach to the promises of the new museology

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Abstract: From open-source software for collection management to open access initiatives for public reuse, the museum community is experiencing an ongoing transformation in what the concept of openness truly means. Adopting the social construction of technology as a theoretical framework and analytical method, this study investigates the changing attitudes and practices among museum professionals, especially how the intellectual precepts of the “new museology” have influenced the conceptualisation and operationalisation of openness. Methodologically, this study explores the archive of the Museums and the Web conference and conducts a qualitative content analysis of papers presented between 1997 and 2020 related to the topic of openness. By identifying and comparing how these papers discussed open-oriented practices, this study demonstrates how museum professionals have socially constructed the changing meanings of openness in the past twenty years and provides empirical evidence about how the new museology discourse has been realised in practice.

Keywords: openness; social construction of technology; new museology; Museums and the Web; content analysis

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Introduction

On February 25, 2020, the Smithsonian Institution launched Smithsonian Open Access, a landmark initiative that released about three million digital collection images and two hundred years of metadata into the public domain. Adopting the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license, the Smithsonian waived its copyright claims and allowed the public to view, download, modify, and share content from this database for free and for any purpose (Fisher & Thomas, 2020). The Smithsonian was far from the first cultural institution to launch an open access initiative, but the unprecedented scale was accompanied by an unfortunate timing, as the announcement came a few weeks before the devastating impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic forced many museums to shut down, some even permanently. As the pursuit of openness took on added urgency during the pandemic, open access initiatives have allowed some of the world’s largest museums to continue engaging with the public online. From Rijksmuseum in

2011, National Gallery of Art in 2012, Metropolitan Museum of Art in 2017, to Smithsonian Institution and British Museum in 2020, open access initiatives have increasingly adopted policy language that expands the meaning of openness from the privilege of access to the right of reuse (K. Kelly, 2013; Pekel, 2014; Tallon, 2017; Wu, 2020).

However, this access-based understanding of openness has not always been the dominant expression among museum practitioners and scholars. From early adoption of open-source software for collection management to recent implementation of open access projects for public reuse, the past few decades have witnessed an ongoing transformation in how the notion of openness is being interpreted and applied by museum professionals around the world. Yet, despite the efforts of several non-profit initiatives to streamline the definition of openness in the cultural context, the actual adoption of open access policies across the GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, museums) sector has been slow and sporadic, with no consensus about what open access truly means in practice. This study considers what openness as a social construct means for the museum community in a post-pandemic world and addresses how the understanding and practice of openness have changed in the museum community.

Theoretically, this paper adopts a social constructivist approach to the use of digital technologies and their related rhetorics in the museum context. This approach considers forms of knowledge as fundamentally social constructs (Pinch & Bijker, 2012). In particular, this study deploys the social construction of technology (SCOT) as a conceptual framework and analytical method to investigate the changing attitudes and practices regarding openness among museum professionals. Particularly relevant within the SCOT framework is the emphasis on how institutionalised social values may shape the practice of individual actors (Klein & Kleinman, 2002). As neoliberal marketisation and reduced public funding forced museums to search for new social relevance, one such set of social values is the “new museology,” a theoretical movement emerging in the late 1980s that sought to redefine the role of museums in society and their changing relationships with the public (Vergo, 1989; Stam, 1993). This study seeks to create a connection between the two bodies of literature and examine how the intellectual precepts of the new museology discourse have shaped the conceptualisation and operationalisation of openness among museum professionals.

Following the Literature Review section on openness in the museum context, the SCOT framework, and the new museology discourse, the Methods section introduces the analytical steps of the study. Methodologically, this study explores the archive of the Museums and the Web conference and performs a qualitative content analysis of papers presented between 1997 and 2020 related to the topic of openness. The Results section presents an overview of how openness was being interpreted to benefit certain social groups, before the Discussion section examines different contextual factors and the amorphous nature of openness as a social construct. By comparing how these papers conceptualise and operationalise openness in the museum context, this study traces how museum professionals have socially constructed the changing meanings of openness in the past twenty years, demonstrating a gradual, albeit not definitive, shift away from an institution-oriented understanding of openness to an access-oriented interpretation that increasingly centred on the needs of the public.

Literature Review

Openness in the museum context

Except for a few high-profile initiatives launched in the past decade, the pursuit of open access across the cultural heritage sector has been rather slow and sporadic, with no consensus about what open access means and what it entails in practice. In a study on open access policies in 11 museums in the U.S., K. Kelly (2013) found conceptual ambiguity and policy inconsistency among different museums about what open access means on the ground for museum workers. Moreover, Kelly suggested that implementing open access is a mission-driven, instead of being merely legal or technological, decision that requires senior-level commitment and is closely related to the museum's institutional identity.

More recently, an ongoing survey launched in 2018 by researchers from the Open GLAM movement (a non-profit initiative that helps cultural institutions open up collection content and data) aims to assess the adoption of open access policies among cultural institutions (McCarthy & Wallace, 2018). Having gathered over 1,600 responses as of July 2023, the survey revealed, based on data at the end of 2020, that open access initiatives often materialised as “individually tailored exceptions, rather than as sector-wide default rules,” with less than 1% of the surveyed institutions having released materials under open access frameworks (Wallace, 2020a).

Despite (or perhaps because of) the slow implementation, the Open GLAM initiative has been trying to establish a working definition of open access and advocating the adoption of actionable policies across the cultural heritage sector. For instance, Wallace (2020b) suggested that the term “open access” is often used to describe initiatives that publish digital collections online for viewing and/or downloading for personal use; without addressing the issue of reuse, especially for commercial purposes, this access-oriented approach fails to provide clarity to users, increases risk in engagement, and ultimately “conflates the status of the platform with the status of the materials.” Beyond cultural institutions, this reuse-oriented interpretation of openness is also championed by the Open Knowledge Foundation (n.d.), the coordinator of the Open GLAM movement, which considers knowledge as open only “if anyone is free to access, use, modify, and share it – subject, at most, to measures that preserve provenance and openness.” Similarly, the emphasis on modification and repurposing resonates with the core principles of the “free and open-source software” movement (see Free Software Foundation, 2021) and the “free cultural works” definition used by Creative Commons to establish its licensing system (Creative Commons, n.d.).

Notwithstanding the differences in terminology, the above efforts to delineate the scope of openness all aim to promote a participatory culture (Jenkins, 2006; Giaccardi, 2012) based on the free exchange of cultural heritage information in the public domain and in so doing preserve the emerging digital commons against increasingly restrictive copyright regimes (Lessig, 2001; Pessach, 2008; Dulong de Rosnay & Stalder, 2020). However, the multiplicity of definitions also attests to the conceptual ambiguity of openness as an amorphous social construct. The next two sections provide a theoretical and analytical framework to explain how the understanding and practice of openness both reflect and reinforce the museum community's deeply institutionalised social values.

Social construction of (museum) technology

Sociologists Trevor Pinch and Wiebe Bijker first developed the social construction of technology (SCOT) model in the 1980s. Highlighting the socially constructed nature of knowledge, SCOT functions as a heuristic that maps out relevant elements in the development of a technological artifact, broadly understood to include both tangible objects/entities, systems, and infrastructures and intangible concepts, values, and ideologies (Hughes, 2012). Within the SCOT framework, Pinch and Bijker (2012) identified four important factors: relevant social groups, interpretative flexibility, stabilisation/closure, and sociopolitical milieu.

First, *relevant social groups* are organisations or groups of individuals who attach the same meanings to a specific artifact. As different groups may attribute different meanings to the same artifact, an *interpretative flexibility* can sometimes emerge. After an alteration of variation and selection, some artifacts gradually become the dominant form, leading to mechanisms for the *stabilisation* of an artifact or the *closure* of debate. Finally, the entire process is situated in a wider *sociopolitical milieu* that influences the meaning-making processes of different social groups by establishing different norms and values. Using this analytical method, Pinch and Bijker demonstrated the non-linear development of the bicycle, paying special attention to how different social groups, such as professional cyclists, women cyclists, and “anti-cyclists,” attached different meanings to the bicycle. It was only after addressing this conflict of interpretation that some models managed to survive, leading to the eventual “invention” of the so-called safety bicycle.

The SCOT framework has received criticisms due to the omission of several important factors. The most prominent criticism centres on the inadequate attention paid to social structure and power relationship that may affect the development of an artifact (Kline & Pinch, 1996). In other words, SCOT fails to consider systematic asymmetries of power between and within social groups, some of whom may be excluded from participating in the design of an artifact (Klein & Kleinman, 2002). For example, museums holding Indigenous artifacts are often faced with ethical dilemmas about the scope of open access projects (Christen, 2012). Indigenous communities constitute a historically underrepresented social group in the interpretation and implementation of openness in part because of the asymmetry of power that excluded them from participating in the museological conversations.

Another criticism suggests that SCOT focuses too much on the design stage of an artifact and that the interpretative flexibility of an already stabilised artifact may become reactivated in the use stage, making users of technology “agents of technological change” (Kline & Pinch, 1996, p. 764). In response to the non-linear nature of interpretative flexibility, Lievrouw (2010) proposed the *determination–contingency framework*: determination represents the imposition of coherence to achieve desired outcomes, while contingency describes the coexistence of different possible conditions. Lievrouw suggested that SCOT scholars identify how moments of determination or contingency have the potential to move development of an artifact in one direction or another. The Smithsonian Open Access announcement is a case in point, which signalled a moment of determination by specifying the conditions of access and the desired outcomes, thus imposing coherence, both semantically and practically, on what open access means in a normative manner.

Finally, Klein and Kleinman (2002) argued that SCOT emphasises agency over *structure*, ignoring “rules of play” that establish the distribution of resources and define the constraints for actors within an organisation; these internal relations may allow some factions to impose their particular interpretation of an artifact, creating “deeply institutionalised social values” that shape the practices of individual actors (p. 40). For instance, the power dynamics between curators and educators may affect resource allocation and thus what openness means for a museum. Positions and departments such as chief digital officers or a digitisation division constitute new social groups that can alter a museum’s internal structure to prioritise different social values regarding the use of digital technologies.

The new museology as institutionalised social values

The SCOT framework highlights the importance of a museum’s organisational structure, internal power relationships, and social values institutionalised in its everyday operations. One such set of social values deeply institutionalised in the museum community in the past few decades is the “new museology,” a theoretical movement emerging in the late 1980s that critically interrogated and redefined the role of museums in society and their changing relations with the public.

Desvallées and Mairesse (2010) traced the origin of a new museology in French literature to the 1970s, which considered the visitor as a participating creator instead of a docile consumer. In the Anglophone discourse, the “new museology” was formally introduced by Vergo (1989), who described a dissatisfaction with the “old” museology that focused “too much about museum methods, and too little about the purposes of museums” (p. 3). Internally, museums prioritised collections and curatorship (McCall & Gray, 2014), while externally serving as cultural authorities that “civilise” and “discipline” the public (Bennett, 1990). In contrast, the “new” museology reconceptualises the museum as a social institution with inherently political roles, emphasising its informational and educational functions (Stam, 1993). Weil (1999) noted a transition of the museum from an “establishment-like institution” that primarily focused on the growth, care, and study of collections to an “entrepreneurial institution” that increasingly focused on providing educational services to the public. This was accompanied by a corresponding shift in the identity of museum professionals from “legislator” to “interpreter” of cultural meanings (M. Ross, 2004).

Weil (1999) identified several factors underlying this paradigm shift. First, a significant decrease in public funding since the 1980s has pressured museums to generate more income on their own and incentivised them to discover and satisfy the needs of the public on its own terms. Second, professional organisations played a more important role in articulating the museum’s ideologies, professional standards, and cultural norms. Weil cited the growing influence of educators within the American Alliance of Museums as evidence of a shift in emphasis from collection care to public service. Finally, M. Ross (2004) argued that a new climate of audience-awareness not only moved museums towards greater accessibility and wider participation but also entangled them with neoliberal market forces that construed the public primarily as consumers.

For all the changing rhetorics, Stam (1993) problematised the new museology, especially how its principles could be translated into practice. Stam observed mixed responses

to the new discourse among museum professionals and found many programs to be “suspiciously *ad hoc*, desperate in tone and curiously at odds with the basic educational purposes of the sponsoring institutions” (p. 268). Weil (1999) also observed a divergence in sentiment between distress about tampering with the centrality of collections and sympathy towards the museum’s evolution to a more educationally oriented organisation. Focusing on curatorial work on the ground, M. Ross (2004) found that new interpretative strategies were “only partial, contingent and limited by what one director described as ‘an in-built resistance to change’” (p. 100). Therefore, the new museology discourse in the 1990s represented a primarily attitudinal change, one that recognised information as a basic and shared museum resource but provided “no blueprint for change” or “manual for survival” and was ultimately “less helpful on praxis” (Stam, 1993, p. 281). More than twenty years later, McCall and Gray (2014) still observed an absence of empirical studies to assess the extent to which the new museology had resulted in substantive changes across the museums sector.

Applying SCOT to understand open practices in museums

Despite the distinct disciplinary origins of the social construction of technology and the new museology, the previous sections have provided several points of convergence that attest to the applicability of SCOT to museum studies. First, the new museological focus on the constructed nature of meanings bestowed on museum objects echoes with the social constructivist approach to the nature of human knowledge. Second, the growing influence of educators inside museums and professional organisations have paved the way for a transformation of institutional identity that increasingly centred on the needs of the public, suggesting, as SCOT scholars would agree, that the empowerment of certain social groups could impact the allocation of resources and the prioritisation of different social values. Finally, the few empirical studies on the impact of the new museology have demonstrated how its transformative discourse can encounter resistance among museum workers, reopening the interpretative flexibility of already stabilised museological principles.

It is based on these points of convergence that this study seeks to contribute to the field of museum studies by mobilising SCOT as a conceptual and analytical framework to interrogate the evolving meanings of openness in the museum context. If the new museology has presented an “escalation in rhetoric” from providing the public with mere refreshment, to education, and to communal empowerment (Weil, 1999, p. 236), how has the understanding and practice of openness escalated along with the movement’s rhetorical development? In other words, if the new museological precepts can be summarised as “from being about something to being for somebody” (Weil, 1999), how have museums changed the ways they conceptualise and operationalise openness to better serve the public rather than merely managing their collections?

Methods

In order to address the changing discourse and practice of openness in the museum community, this study explores the archive of the Museums and the Web (MW) conference and analyses conference papers presented between 1997 and 2020 related

to the topic of openness. The MW conference first started in 1997, convened every year in North America and/or Asia, and claims to be the world’s largest museum innovation and technology conference, attended by a wide array of participants, including educators, curators, librarians, designers, researchers, consultants, developers, and publishers (Museums and the Web, 2020). Another potential source of data is the annual conference organised by MCN (Museum Computer Network) since 1968. While MCN’s longer history would have presented more historical insights, it unfortunately does not publish any conference proceedings (except for select session recordings since 2011). Attempts to access and publish these conference papers have been sporadic and irregular (Marty & Kim, 2020), making MCN conferences an unlikely source of data for this study.

This study conducts a qualitative content analysis of a select body of MW conference papers. Between 1997 and 2020, a total number of 1,416 papers have been archived on the MW website, of which 37 articles include the word “open” either in the title or the list of keywords; one paper is excluded from analysis as it discusses openness only in passing as “openness to interchange.” The remaining 36 papers, summarised in the Appendix, were presented by (co)authors from 47 institutions located in 35 cities from 10 countries. When each institution is counted once for every paper they co-presented, the 47 institutions represented 56 occurrences that this study further categorises into five groups: *university*, *LAM*, *non-profit*, *vendor*, and *independent* (Table 1).

Table 1. Five types of presenting institutions (including unaffiliated individuals).

Type	Description	Occurrence	Percentage
university	-	22	35.7%
LAM	libraries, archives, and museums	20	39.3%
non-profit	including government agencies	7	12.5%
vendor	companies providing commercial products or services	4	7.1%
independent	freelance or unaffiliated individuals	3	5.4%

Although institutions of various types and sizes are included in this dataset, it is important to emphasise the limitations of focusing on just one body of texts generated from one professional forum that, due to its nature of selectivity (e.g., language and regional focus), may have excluded other museum professionals and their alternative voices. Indeed, the 36 papers included in this study originated from only ten, mostly western developed countries, with institutions located in the U.S., Netherlands, and UK particularly overrepresented (Table 2). Therefore, findings based on the MW paper archive should not be generalised to represent the entire museum community.

To analyse these 36 conference papers, this study adopts a combination of open and axial coding (Corbin & Strauss, 2015) performed using the data analysis software ATLAS.ti and, informed by the SCOT framework, summarises each paper based on the following template:

Through [*open interpretations*], museums can achieve [*goals*] for the benefit of [*relevant social groups*], if [*challenges*] can be overcome.

Here, [*open interpretations*] refer to the open-related concept or practice presented in the paper (e.g., an open-source software or an open access database); [*relevant social groups*] refer to specific social groups (e.g., researchers, educators, or local

Table 2. Geographic distribution of the presenting institutions.

Country	Occurrence	Percentage	Country	Occurrence	Percentage
United States	16	41.0%	Australia	1	2.6%
Netherlands	7	17.9%	Chile	1	2.6%
United Kingdom	7	17.9%	France	1	2.6%
Canada	3	7.7%	Greece	1	2.6%
			Italy	1	2.6%
			New Zealand	1	2.6%

communities) that the open-related concept or practices are intended to serve. Therefore, to address the research question of the study entails mapping out what [*open interpretations*] have been presented over the years and whether the intended [*relevant social groups*] have changed to signal a shift from fulfilling the functions of internal departments to serving the needs of the wider public. In addition to these core elements adapted from the SCOT framework, [*goals*] and [*challenges*] provide important contextual information that grounds the discussion of these open-related concepts and practices.

Results

Analyses of the 36 conference papers have identified seven relevant social groups and 17 open interpretations. Based on the analytical template introduced in the Methods section and the results of the content analysis, Table 3 shows the distribution of all the relevant social groups and open interpretations over the years. Each row represents one paper:

- The *Date* column shows the year in which the paper was presented.
- *Relevant Social Groups* mentioned in the paper are marked in columns to the left.
- *Open Interpretations* mentioned in the paper are marked in columns to the right.
- The number of occurrences for each keyword is shown in the parentheses.

For instance, the paper 2013b is about the use of [*open data*] and [*open license*] to serve the needs of the [*museum*] and [*researchers*], whereas the paper 2020a is about the use of [*open source*] to serve the needs of the [*museum*], [*users*], and external [*educators*]. The title of each paper and detailed information about the presenting institutions can be found in the Appendix. Finally, it is important to emphasise, due to the limited sample size, that these numbers should not be used to perform any statistical inference. Instead, analyses presented in the following sections should only serve as a heuristic to map out some of the major elements that address the research question of the study.

Relevant social groups

A total number of seven different relevant social groups are identified in the papers. Their description and number of occurrences are shown in Table 4. The label *museum*

Table 4. Relevant social groups identified in the papers.

Social Group	Description	Occurrence
museum	GLAMs and other cultural institutions (e.g., historical centres)	36
user	including visitors, audiences, users, communities, and the general public	15
collaborator	outside the institution (e.g., software developers or other institutions)	10
researcher	outside the institution (e.g., universities or research centres)	9
educator	outside the institution (e.g., schools or teachers)	7
staff	inside the institution, whenever specified (e.g., curators or docents)	5
subject	humans subjects in still and moving images	1

refers to all types of cultural institutions; *user* includes in-person visitors, online users, audiences, communities, and the general public; *collaborator*, *researcher*, and *educator* refer to those from outside the institution; *staff* refers to departments or functions,

whenever specified, inside the institution, such as curators and docents; *subject* refers to human subjects that appear in still and moving images.

Despite the wide range of social groups, the notion of the public was not always recognised, especially in papers presented before the 2010s. Understandably, *museums* were included in all the papers, but when they were the only relevant group (Goodman et al., 2007; B. Kelly et al., 2007; Walk, 2009), it means that the open-related practices were intended to serve the museum itself instead of the needs of the public. Although these institution-centred papers were mostly presented in the 2000s, they continued to be included well into the late 2010s (Roddis & Farquhar, 2018; Wilson, 2019). Nonetheless, *staff* became increasingly acknowledged as heterogeneous social (sub)groups within the museum, signalling a growing awareness that the museum was not a homogeneous entity without differentiated values and priorities. For instance, Winesmith (2013) described the experience of the Museum of Contemporary Art Australia when revamping its digital infrastructure:

Some staff do not like change, especially when it might mean more work for them. In these cases it's important to explain the whole project and their part within it and to reiterate the importance of the visitor experience, rather than appearing to force them to change without contextualising their work.

Acknowledge that you have two key audiences; museum visitors (physical and digital) and museum staff. In doing so, we avoided solutions that only benefits one group.

Collaborators were increasingly recognised in papers presented since the 2010s, ranging from developers of open-source software and hardware (Ketner, 2012; Langer & Alderman, 2016), content creators reusing museum collections for creative production (Oomen et al., 2012), and digital platforms such as Wikipedia and Flickr for sharing images and metadata (Antonini et al., 2014; Kingston & Edgar, 2015). The increasing contributions made by external collaborators were explicitly acknowledged in one paper through what is known as Joy's Law: "No matter who you are, most of the smartest people work for someone else" (quoted in Oomen et al., 2012).

Other relevant social groups include *researchers*, *educators*, and *users*. Many early papers focused exclusively on the benefits of open-related practices for scholarly research (Perkins, 2001; Cole et al., 2002; Fleming et al., 2008). *Educators* were rarely discussed until 2015 but have been featured regularly since then. Similarly, *users* were hardly mentioned in the 2000s but became more frequently discussed in the 2010s. For instance, Oomen et al. (2011) made the following comments when sharing the "Picture War Monuments" project coordinated by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision:

[Museums] are currently exploring which roles mobile devices can play in meeting demands by users expecting to play an active rather than passive role as they seek to explore 'their' heritage. ... We also wanted to explore active engagement by inviting users to share their knowledge and content. This sharing is part of a bigger trend within the heritage domain of facilitating active user engagement using emerging technology.

Similarly, it has also been recognised that "for [museum] content to be truly accessible, it needs to be where the users are, embedded in their daily networked lives"

(Waibel & Erway, quoted in Baltussen et al., 2013). These user-oriented comments resonated with the broader participatory turn in museum studies around the 2010s (Simon, 2010; Giaccardi, 2012; Kidd, 2014; Bautista, 2014; Laws, 2015). Moreover, the idea of “meeting users where they are” represented the kind of “marketing” mode Weil (1999) noted, where museums, responding to the increasing marketisation in the cultural sector, actively attempted to identify and satisfy the needs of the public rather than convincing the public to buy what they had to offer in the traditional “selling” mode.

Interpretative flexibility

A total number of 17 open interpretations are identified in the papers. The number of occurrences for each interpretation is shown in Table 5. Despite the long list of various interpretations, the most frequently discussed ones – open source, open data, open license, open access, and open standards – demonstrated a lopsided focus on the internal functions of the museum rather than its external social responsibilities. Open source, open data, and open standards initiatives allow museums to improve database useability and collection management. In contrast, open license and open access are unambiguously public-oriented because they provide and specify the legal and technical conditions under which the public can access and reuse the museum’s collections.

It is thus important to observe that practices based on open source, open data, and open standards have been regularly presented over the years, whereas only five papers (Bray, 2009; Muñoz, 2011; Kingston & Edgar, 2015; Roddis & Farquhar, 2018; J. Ross et al., 2018) discussed real-world open access initiatives that centred the needs of the public as opposed to the museum itself. One of them in fact reflected on the very limitation of open access, regarding the museum’s legal and moral rights to share images of members from Indigenous communities:

Still, the real and, I think, deeper problem is an ethical one. I feel uncomfortable posting unpublished material on the website to allow people to publish or use it when they do not know the people who were filmed and when they do not have the express permission of those subjects to use the recordings. (Muñoz, 2011)

This kind of ethical reflection, highlighting Indigenous communities as a previously, if not still, underrepresented social group, strengthened the interpretative flexibility of openness by challenging the perception of open access as an unconditionally positive development.

In addition, some papers exhibited a heightened interpretative flexibility by critically reflecting on what openness *could* mean for the museum community. For instance, B. Kelly et al. (2008) outlined the multiple dimensions of openness and explored how

Table 5. Open interpretations identified in the papers.

Interpretation	Occurrence	Interpretation	Occurrence	Interpretation	Occurrence
open source	14	open API	2	open collaboration	1
open data	12	open archive	2	open culture	1
open license	6	open content	2	open GLAM	1
open access	5	open hardware	2	open MOOC	1
open standards	4	open innovation	2	open museum	1
		open service	2	open participation	1

they could be applied in practice. Similarly, Dawson et al. (2017) used the term “open movement” to characterise different aspects of openness such as open standards, open source, open hardware, open data, open participation, and open innovation. J. Ross et al. (2018), on the other hand, cautioned against what they called “progressive openness,” where issues of digitisation and copyright were prioritised over open data and open standards, resulting in a “utopian” conception of openness that overlooked its political implications, such as the exclusion of certain voices because of the blind pursuit of openness. In any case, these three highly reflective papers attributed different meanings to openness, demonstrating both its culturally constructed nature and its inherent interpretative flexibility.

Discussion

Overall, the 36 MW conference papers have presented a growing range of relevant social groups, and while an institution-oriented understanding of openness has persisted, the public has become increasingly recognised over the years, indicating an overall attitudinal change in line with the new museology literature. In the meantime, despite the wide variety of open interpretations, these papers have consistently focused on using openness to serve the museum’s internal functions and scholarly research, and it was not until the 2010s that the rhetoric of public access became one of the museum’s primary concerns. These developments occurred in a broad sociopolitical milieu, but contrary to the SCOT framework, the multifaceted meanings of openness have never been stabilised enough to reach a complete closure.

Openness and the wider sociopolitical milieu

Open-related museum practices are situated in multiple layers of contexts: international, national, institutional, and non-profit. This was best exemplified by Kingston and Edgar (2015), who described how the Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa undertook an open access initiative responding to three different contexts. Internationally, the museum studied well-known open access projects at the British Library, Rijksmuseum, National Gallery of Art, and more. Nationally, open data and open access were emerging as a priority for the New Zealand government. Internally, the museum itself also began to prioritise sharing authority with the public. For the authors, these important contextual considerations informed the museum’s long-term commitment to open access initiatives.

Similarly, Dawson et al. (2017) recognised “open government” in Canada as the driving force behind the open movement in the cultural heritage sector. Several other papers also commented on the changing organisational context and articulated the need for structural changes within the museum, so that cross-departmental collaboration could promote open practices (Dawson et al., 2017; J. Ross et al., 2018). This consideration of organisational changes echoed with the SCOT framework’s focus on structural elements, which establish the distribution of resources, professional capacities, and ultimately institutional power.

Finally, Kapsalis (2016), albeit not a paper from the MW conference, highlighted the role of private donors and charitable foundations in promoting open access. Several major funders of cultural institutions in the U.S. (e.g., Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and Ford Foundation) “have made open access either a requirement for grant recipients or a factor in assessing potential grantees” (p. 6). Considering the museum’s increasing reliance on private funding, it is important to consider this non-profit context, in which museums may be incentivised to prioritise open access over other open-related goals to attract private donations.

“Open is as open does”

The SCOT literature postulates the stabilisation of an artifact’s interpretation throughout its developmental process. However, despite the emerging rhetoric of public access and reuse, authors presenting at the MW conferences have remained committed to practices that facilitate the museum’s internal functions and scholarly research. In other words, the stabilisation of the meanings of openness was never truly achieved. Using Lievrouw’s (2010) *determination–contingency framework*, one might argue that despite moments of determination (e.g., open access initiatives and efforts to define openness) that gravitated to an access-oriented interpretation of openness, moments of contingency, due to the various relevant social groups and their different norms and values, persisted to pull museums in multiple directions, perpetuating the interpretative flexibility of openness as a social construct.

Alternatively, Hughes (1983) argued that values, ideas, and institutions developed around certain technologies would create *technological momentum*, “the propensity of technologies to develop along previously defined trajectories unless and until deflected by some powerful external force” (Constant, 2012, p. 223). Regarding openness in the museum context, the “previously defined trajectories” stemmed in part from the community of software developers, where open source remains an important idea and practice; they also stemmed from the values of those who chose to present at the MW conferences and those within the conference who decided to accept these papers. These elements could have contributed to the persistence of certain understanding of openness. By contrast, high-profile open access initiatives, private foundations incentivising open access, and the Open GLAM movement are “powerful external forces” that seek to reorient the conceptualisation of openness towards the needs of the general public. Therefore, it is in a tussle with such technological momentum that the conference papers exhibited a dual focus on both the museum’s internal operations and its external responsibilities.

Finally, it may be useful to consider what Star and Griesemer (1989) termed *boundary objects*, which are

... both plastic enough to adapt to local needs and the constraints of the several parties employing them, yet robust enough to maintain a common identity across sites. They are weakly structured in common use, and become strongly structured in individual-site use. These objects may be abstract or concrete. They have different meanings in different social worlds but their structure is common enough to more than one world to make them recognisable, a means of translation. (p. 393)

Indeed, openness is plastic enough to adapt to the local needs of museum professionals and robust enough to maintain a common meaning across the cultural heritage sector. The concept of openness may be abstract and amorphous, but each of its museological instantiation carries concrete and material implications, or as van Tuijn et al. (2016) put it, “Open is as open does.” Openness therefore exhibits such boundary quality and plays the role of translation among different social groups, who may engage with open practices in different manners but ultimately serve a common goal to fulfil the museum’s institutional and social functions.

Conclusion

In a post-pandemic world, rethinking what openness means for the museum community has never been more important. This study contributes to the field of museum studies by applying the social construction of technology to explore how the changing meanings of openness have aligned with broader institutional changes prescribed by the new museology. Analyses of 36 MW conference papers have revealed a growing range of relevant social groups, and the wider public indeed became increasingly recognised over the years, notwithstanding a persistent institution-oriented emphasis on the museum’s internal functions. Similarly, the broad array of open interpretations has foregrounded an access-centred interpretation of openness since the 2010s, despite a persistent commitment to interpretations that prioritise collection management and scholarly research. These findings suggest a partial and incomplete shift away from the museum-centred to the public-oriented understanding of openness, demonstrating the overall attitudinal change described in the new museology discourse.

As is mentioned in the Methods section, performing a qualitative content analysis on the archived MW conference papers has its limitations. Since the 36 papers analysed in this study represented only ten countries, future research could adopt a similar approach to analyse other bodies of texts, preferably from non-English speaking parts of the world. Analysing accepted papers also takes for granted the human role of conference organisers and reviewers, who are a relevant social group in and of themselves. Future research may benefit from adding ethnographic approaches by examining the decision-making processes of this particular group. Finally, this study performed a close reading on a small sample of conference papers, but future research could employ linguistic and/or computational techniques to analyse a larger body of texts, conducting, for instance, a meta-analysis on how previous academic journal articles discuss openness from a semantic and diachronic perspective. Ultimately, analyses and arguments presented in this paper aim to serve as a heuristic that maps out some of the major elements that address the changing meaning of openness.

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The author reports there are no competing interests to declare.

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Appendix

Information about the 36 MW conference papers.

Author (Year)	Title	Type	Institution Country, City
Perkins (2001)	A New Way of Making Cultural Information Resources Visible on the Web: Museums and the Open Archives Initiative	Computer Interchange of Museum Information Non-Profit	Canada, Tantalton
Cole et al. (2002)	Now That We've Found The 'Hidden Web,' What Can We Do with It?	University	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign United States, Champaign
Goodman et al. (2007a)	OpenCollection Web-Based Collection Cataloguing and Access Software	LAM	Museum of the Moving Image United States, New York City
		Vendor	Whirl-i-Gig United States, New York City
B. Kelly et al. (2007b)	Addressing The Limitations of Open Standards	University	University of Bath United Kingdom, Bath
		University	King's College London United Kingdom, London
B. Kelly et al. (2008a)	What Does Openness Mean to The Museum Community?	University	University of Bath United Kingdom, Bath
		University	University of Oxford United Kingdom, Oxford
		Non-Profit	Eduserv United Kingdom, Bath
Fleming et al. (2008b)	The Meta Art Museum: Towards the Promise of an Open Collaboration Platform	LAM	Museum of Fine Arts, Boston United States, Boston
		University	Massachusetts Institute of Technology United States, Cambridge
Bray (2009a)	Open Licensing and the Future for Collections	LAM	Powerhouse Museum Australia, Sydney
Walk (2009b)	Software as a Service and Open APIs	University	University of Bath United Kingdom, Bath
Muñoz (2011a)	Opening Anthropological Archives to the World. Do I have the Right to Upload?	LAM	Chilean Museum of Pre-Columbian Art Chile, Santiago
Oomen et al. (2011b)	Picture War Monuments: Creating an Open Source Location Based Mobile Platform	LAM	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision Netherlands, Hilversum
		University	Utrecht University Netherlands, Utrecht
Ketner (2012a)	Open Innovation and Open Source: A Guide for Content Developers	LAM	Tech Museum of Innovation United States, San Jose
Oomen et al. (2012b)	Sharing cultural heritage the linked open data way: why you should sign up		Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

		LAM	Netherlands, Hilversum
		University	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam Netherlands, Amsterdam
Voss (2012c)	Radically Open Cultural Heritage Data on the Web	Non-Profit	We Are What We Do United States, San Francisco
			-
Baltussen et al. (2013a)	Open Culture Data: Opening GLAM Data Bottom-up	Independent	Netherlands
		LAM	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision Netherlands, Hilversum
		Non-Profit	Kennisland Netherlands, Amsterdam
Henry & Brown (2013b)	Serving Tea on the Rapids: An Architectural Approach for Managing Linked Open Data	LAM	Missouri History Museum United States, St. Louis
Parsell (2013c)	Using Open Source tools to expose YCBA collection data in the LIDO schema for OAI-PMH harvesting	LAM	Yale Center for British Art United States, New Haven
Winesmith (2013d)	Open systems, loosely coupled: Creating an integrated museum eCommerce system for the MCA	LAM	San Francisco Museum of Modern Art United States, San Francisco
			Polytechnic University of Milan
Antonini et al. (2014a)	Archeowiki: When open-source strategies attract visitors' presence in museums. A project for the enhancement of archaeological heritage in Lombardy (Italy)	University	Italy, Milan
		Non-Profit	Gruppo Archeologico Ambrosiano Italy, Milan
Palin (2014b)	Free, open and mobile. An open platform solution changes the rules of the game into museums	Vendor	izi.TRAVEL Netherlands, Amsterdam
Szekely et al. (2014c)	Karma: Tools for Mapping Collection Meta-Data to Linked Open Data	University	University of Southern California United States, Los Angeles
Kingston & Edgar (2015a)	A review of a year of open access images at Te Papa	LAM	Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa New Zealand, Wellington
			InnoVision
Dupuy et al. (2015b)	Towards open museums: The interconnection of digital and physical spaces in open environments	Vendor	France, Paris
		University	Paris Nanterre University France, Nanterre
Sissman (2015c)	A new DOR opens: How the J. Paul Getty Museum is reimagining digital collection information management	LAM	J. Paul Getty Museum United States, Los Angeles
			New Mexico Highlands University
Langer & Alderman (2016a)	Open hardware belongs in your museum	University	United States, Las Vegas, NM
		Non-Profit	Balboa Park Online Collaborative United States, San Diego
Parry et al. (2016b)	Why MOOCs matter: The consequence of massive open online courses for museums, universities, and their publics	University	University of Leicester United Kingdom, Leicester
van Tuijn et al. (2016c)	Open is as open does. How to use open content in a personalized interactive museum exhibit	LAM	Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision Netherlands, Hilversum

		Independent	Netherlands
Dawson et al. (2017a)	Open Innovation: Open Movements and The Role of a Museum in the 21st Century	Canada's Museums of Science and Innovation LAM	Canada, Ottawa
Newbury (2017b)	Art Tracks: Using Linked Open Data for Object Provenance in Museums	LAM	Carnegie Museum of Art United States, Pittsburgh
Roddis & Farquhar (2018a)	From At Risk to Open Access: The Endangered Archives of The World	Vendor LAM	Cogapp United Kingdom, Brighton The British Library United Kingdom, London
J. Ross et al. (2018b)	Digital Collections, Open Data and The Boundaries of Openness: A Case Study from The National Galleries of Scotland	University LAM LAM	University of Edinburgh United Kingdom, Edinburgh Royal Ontario Museum Canada, Toronto National Galleries of Scotland United Kingdom, Edinburgh
Berreth (2019a)	Simple Tangible Interaction: An Illumination of Trajan's Weapons Frieze and Open-source Models for Exhibition Development and Hands-on Storytelling	University	North Carolina State University United States, Raleigh
Valeonti et al. (2019b)	Examining Mobile Print-on-Demand as an Alternative to Image Licensing for Monetizing Digitization to Promote OpenGLAM	University University LAM	University College London United Kingdom, London University of Edinburgh United Kingdom, Edinburgh Metropolitan Organisation of Museums of Visual Arts of Thessaloniki Greece, Thessaloniki
Villaespesa & Navarrete (2019c)	Museum Collections on Wikipedia: Opening Up to Open Data Initiatives	University University	Pratt Institute United States, New York City Erasmus University Rotterdam Netherlands, Rotterdam
Wilson (2019d)	Constructing a Converged Open Source Museum Platform	Independent	- United States
Connelly & Frechette (2020a)	Designing CLIO, An Open-Source Toolkit for Museum Pop-Up Digital Interactives	University University	University of Washington United States, Seattle Central Seattle College United States, Seattle
Lemmens (2020b)	The Other Interface. Using linked (open) data to provide a different kind of access	Non-Profit	Stichting DEN Netherlands, The Hague